

Project title: All Data 4 Green Deal - An Integrated, FAIR Approach for the Common European Data Space

Project number: 101061001

Project Acronym: AD4GD

Type: HORIZON-AG - HORIZON Action Grant Budget-Based

Work program topics addressed: HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01

DELIVERABLE No: D6.3

SCALABILITY, PERFORMANCE, AND TECHNOLOGY CONVERGENCE POTENTIAL ASSESSMENT

Due date of deliverable: 31/08/2025

Actual submission date: 19/08/2025

Version: 1.0

Main Authors: Cédric Crettaz (IoT Lab), Anna Brékine (IoT Lab), George Salukvadze (IoT Lab)

DOCUMENT METADATA

Project number	101061001
Project title	All Data 4 Green Deal - An Integrated, FAIR Approach for the Common European Data Space

Deliverable title	Scalability, performance, and technology convergence assessment
Deliverable number	D6.3
Deliverable version	1.0
Contractual date of delivery	31/08/2025
Actual date of delivery	19/08/2025
Document status	Final
Document version	1.0
Online access	https://ad4gd.eu/deliverables/ and https://zenodo.org/communities/ad4gd
Dissemination	PU - Public
Work package	WP6: Pilots, Tests and Validation
Partner responsible	IoT Lab (ITL)
Author(s)	Cédric Crettaz (IoT Lab), Anna Brékine (IoT Lab), George Salukvadze (IoT Lab), Ignacio EliceGUI (ATOS), Thomas Hodson (ECMWF), Christian Borger

	(ECMWF), Ivette Serral (CREAF)
Editor(s)	Cédric Crettaz (IoT Lab), Anna Brékine (IoT Lab), George Salukvadze (IoT Lab)
Reviewer(s)	Piotr Zabrowski (OGC), Francesca Noardo (OGC)
EC Project Officer	Lara Congiu

Abstract	The deliverable D6.3 presents the assessment related to the scalability, the performance and to the technology convergence in the context of the three pilots implemented by the AD4GD project. The reader of this document should be familiar with the architecture of the project described in other deliverables such as D5.2 and D6.2. This document does not include any schema or diagram of the AD4GD architecture. Please refer to other deliverables for diagrams of the AD4GD or pilot architectures.
Keywords	Scalability, performance, optimization, interoperability, edge cloud, cloud computing
Disclaimer	Views and opinions expressed in this deliverable are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the United Kingdom, or Switzerland. Neither the European Union nor United Kingdom nor Switzerland can be held responsible for them.

DOCUMENT VERSION HISTORY

Version history			
Version	Date	Modification reason	Modified by
0.1	14/11/2024	Initial version of the document	Cédric Crettaz (IoT Lab)
0.2	14/03/2025	First draft	Cédric Crettaz (IoT Lab)
0.3	26/05/2025	Inputs from IoT Lab	Cédric Crettaz (IoT Lab)
0.4	02/06/2025	Inputs for the scalability	Cédric Crettaz (IoT Lab)
0.5	18/06/2025	Inputs related to the performance	Cédric Crettaz (IoT Lab)
0.6	20/06/2025	Inputs concerning the technology convergence assessment	Cédric Crettaz (IoT Lab)
0.7	25/06/2025	Contributions from ATOS	Ignacio Elicegui (ATOS)
0.8	30/06/2025	Contributions from ECMWF	Thomas Hodson and Christian Borger (ECMWF)
0.9	16/07/2025	Contributions on Pilot 2	Ivette Serral (CREAF)
0.10	17/07/2025	Deliverable ready for internal review	Cédric Crettaz (IoT Lab)
0.11	01/08/2025	Internal review	Piotr Zaborowski (OGC)
1.0	04/08/2025	Deliverable ready for submission	Cédric Crettaz (IoT Lab)
1.0	19/08/2025	Final coordinator review	Joan Maso (CREAF)

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CTMS	Camera Trap Metadata Standard
CRUD	Create, Read, Update and Delete
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation-Linked Data

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Transport
NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interfaces Linked Data
NGSI-v2	Next Generation Service Interfaces version 2
O&M	Observations and Measurements
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PaaS	Platform as a Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
STA	SensorThings API
STApplus	SensorThings API plus
SWE	Sensor Web Enablement
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

Table of Contents

Executive summary	8
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Purpose of the deliverable	9
2 Scalability assessment	10
2.1 Methodology and Experiments	10
2.2 Results	11
3 Performance assessment	15
3.1 Methodology and Experiments	15
3.2 Results	17
4 Technology convergence assessment	21
4.1 Methodology and Experiments	21
4.2 Results	22
5 Global Results	23
6 Conclusions and recommendations	23
7 References	25

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable D6.3 “Scalability, performance, and technology convergence potential assessment” describes the results of the AD4GD project concerning the assessment of the pilots for the following technical topics: scalability, performance and technology convergence potential. This deliverable presents the methodology used for each topic to assess the outcomes of the project, in particular for the three pilots implemented during the whole duration of the AD4GD project. Several experiments and tests were realised to evaluate the performance and the scalability of the Green Deal Data Space building blocks developed and used during the project. The results obtained after the assessment done in the context of the Task T6.5 show that important improvements were realised concerning the scalability and the performance during the development of the GDDS building blocks. Some recommendations were elaborated based on the results of the AD4GD project, in particular the lessons learnt from the three pilots.

This study does not include considerations on the impact of the use of the Eclipse Dataspace Connector in the architecture.

1 INTRODUCTION

The WP6 is in charge of the three AD4GD pilots, in particular the development of application prototypes implemented in function of the needs and requirements collected in the pilots at the initial phase of the project. The WP6 is also responsible for the assessment of the benefits of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) for the different stakeholders involved in the three pilots.

The Task T6.5 is dedicated to determine the potential of the data space in terms of scalability, performance and interoperability. The analysis is based on the outcomes collected in the three pilots, namely the small lakes in Berlin, the biodiversity in the region of Catalonia and the air quality. Different experiments were realised with the data collected in the context of the AD4GD pilots.

The reader of this document should be familiar with the architecture of the project described in other deliverables such as D5.2 and D6.2. This document does not include any schema or diagram of the AD4GD architecture. Please refer to other deliverables for diagrams of the AD4GD or pilot architectures.

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The main objective of this deliverable is the assessment of the scalability, the performance and the technology convergence based on the experimentations done in the three pilots using the building blocks developed in the AD4GD project.

The deliverable is composed in fact by three sorts of assessments concerning all the three pilots:

- Scalability assessment
- Performance assessment
- Technology convergence assessment

For each sort of assessments, the used methodology applied in the different experiments is described, followed by explanations of the collected results. This process permits a complete analysis of the global results and the generation of practical recommendations for the future development of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS).

2 SCALABILITY ASSESSMENT

The scalability is playing a very important role in the context of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS). Indeed, a lot of data should be collected during the whole duration of the AD4GD project. This implies that the design of the future Green Deal Data Space is aligned with the needs and the requirements elaborated during the first phase of the AD4GD project. The following sections present the methodology, the experiments and the results to evaluate the good implementation of the scalability in the GDDS design.

2.1 METHODOLOGY AND EXPERIMENTS

First of all, the notion of scalability in the context of the Green Deal Data Space implies that some specific requirements should be followed and implemented. The elaboration and the choice of the requirements associated to the scalability were realised at the beginning of the AD4GD project, taken into account of course the particular needs of the three pilots.

The methodology is designed to determine the most relevant requirements in relationship with the scalability and then, to realise some experiments to assess the scalability in the context of the future Green Deal Data Space. The list of requirements is given below:

1. **Computing resources:** In the context of the AD4GD project, it is important to have sufficient resources to execute the predictions implemented as AI/ML modules. This requirement was taken into account in the first steps of the project when the architecture of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) was elaborated. Indeed, a HPC cluster was put in place to get the necessary computing resources. Details of this HPC cluster can be found in D5.1.
2. **Storage capacity:** Different kinds of data are collected in the three pilots and thus, the storage should be sufficient to keep the data in the Green Deal Data Space. Different building blocks of the GDDS offer the required storage capacity, such as the MinIO server and the FROST/STApplus instances.
3. **Network availability:** As the different sorts of data are distributed among different physical and virtual locations, it is necessary to have a good connectivity through notably the Internet. Taking into account the presence of IoT sensors, which are often constrained devices with limited possibilities for communication and computing, some experiments have been realised to ensure that the network availability, in particular the network bandwidth, is ensured for the objectives of the AD4GD project.
4. **Concurrency and parallelism:** Multiple data sources are available at the same time and it is essential to collect, store and handle the heterogeneous data in parallel. Different mechanisms are available and were studied during the project in the context of the three pilots.

5. **Caching:** The caching allows reducing the number of requests to any types of servers. One of the benefits of caching is also the time to response which is reduced, too. Furthermore, this requirement permits to improve the user friendliness of the solution proposed by the AD4GD project.
6. **Queueing system:** Queueing is a good mechanism to handle numerous requests in an asynchronous manner. It allows to process requests more efficiently and faster than other systems such as synchronous processing. Typically, the MQTT protocol is implemented a queueing system by design.
7. **Extensibility:** As the Green Deal Data Space is evolving in function of the time, but also in function of new types of data available, it is required that the GDDS design takes into account the possibilities to add new building blocks or components into the data space. The integration should be of course easy for the stakeholders and developers involved in the management and the maintenance of the future GDDS.

2.2 RESULTS

The first requirement is the sufficient number of computing resources available in the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS). To implement this requirement, a HPC cluster was sized and installed on the PSNC premises. The WP5 has defined the hardware architecture meeting the needs of the pilots, in particular for the AI/ML modules. The different experiments made in this context have confirmed the distribution of computing resources described in the deliverable D5.1 “AI, ML in HPC and cloud for FAIR Science Services”. Considering the initial analysis of the AD4GD Data Space and the AI module, the HPC architecture relies on:

- 2 master nodes:
 - Master-0, with 8 CPUs and 16 GB of RAM
 - Master-1, with 32 CPUs and 32 GB of RAM
- 4 worker nodes
 - Workers 1 –2 – 3 with 16 CPUs and 32 GB of RAM each
 - Worker 4 with 32 CPUs and 32 GB of RAM
- 1 Network File System (NFS) Server, supported by 8 CPUs and 8 GB of RAM, and offering 1 TB of storing capabilities

Taking into account also the internal storage assigned to each node (40GB), it makes a total resources set of:

- 130 CPUs
- 188 GB of RAM
- 1320 GB of storage (plus a reserved storage of 680 GB to be redistributed according to project and pilot needs)

This selected distribution responds to two specific criteria:

- a virtual server layout (master and worker nodes) designed to build a Kubernetes cluster, which allows a controlled deployment of the required applications and services as containers.
- a dimensioning of the workers' nodes (32 GB of RAM) intended to support the training of the prediction models for pilots.

The storage is also an important point during the design of the future GDDS. In the AD4GD project, the storage to receive the heterogeneous data and serve the AI models is implemented by the MinIO server hosted on the HPC cluster. It works as the project's centralized data repository and it contains (among others) the raw data (typically the CSV files coming from different data sources and land usage images), the processed information harmonised in JSON-LD files (including merged tables and predictions), images processed by the biodiversity models and the AI models developed in project pilots. Finally, the storage available on the HPC cluster can reach 2 TB.

The Kubernetes cluster approach implemented to support the AD4GD Data Space, including its centralised repository abstracts it from the hardware resources, which reinforces two relevant features:

- The **replicability** of the designed data space, which can be easily deployed in other Kubernetes clusters, by applying the corresponding receipts (YAML files) and configurations used to build the original one.
- The **scalability**, because Kubernetes is designed to nimbly support the addition and management of new servers (horizontal scalability), as well as modifying the existing nodes (vertical scalability), both of which increase the overall cluster resources.

The FROST/STApplus server instances also saved the data using the data format specified by the OGC SensorThings API. The size of the data storage has been evaluated using the different kinds of data available for the three pilots. Each FROST/STApplus server instance has an available storage varying from 50 GB to 100 GB, which can be extended in function of the needs of the three pilots.

At the level of the network, a particular care was dedicated to the edge because the IoT sensors are very often installed in remote places where the network availability and the bandwidth are limited. For instance, several IoT sensors measuring the water quality and level are placed in the small lakes of the city of Berlin in remote areas. Some improvements and related experiments were undertaken during the AD4GD project and are reported in the deliverable D3.2 "Scalability and edge computing optimization".

These experiments show that some relatively simple implementations at the edge or at the cloud can increase the scalability when the network is limited, typically when IoT sensors are installed in remote areas without a good Internet connection. The first related experiment

reduced the number of useless data when the data are wrong or incomplete. Indeed, when the network connexion is rather bad, there are more errors during the transmission of IoT data. Filtering mechanisms were put in place to remove these wrong data, in particular the data generated by the IoT sensors installed in the small lakes of the city of Berlin. The utilisation of a Kalman filter in a second experiment reduces almost the volume of IoT data with factor 2. It is indeed useless to send identical data from the edge to the cloud. To achieve this, only when the values are sufficiently different from the previous ones, a packet of new data is sent to the FROST/STApplus server. In a third experiment, the utilisation of batch requests to a FROST/STApplus server reduces the time necessary to send and store the data through the OGC SensorThings API, which is playing an essential role in the proposed GDDS architecture. The complete process to use the batch feature provided by the OGC SensorThings API is described in details in the deliverable D3.2.

To increase the scalability, different experiments were undertaken during the AD4GD project to parallelise some data processing activities. The concurrency and the parallelism are indeed important when sending and retrieving a lot of data to/from an instance of a FROST/STApplus server. The experiments executed concerning this aspect were done using the historical data provided by the Sensor.Community platform. Indeed, a high number of air quality sensors are available through the Sensor.Community online portal; these IoT sensors are generating a lot of heterogeneous data, as there are several sorts of air quality sensors which are directly connected to the Sensor.Community platform. The programming language used for these experiments is Java, because Java is offering a much better support for the concurrency and the parallelism than Python. The obtained results are very satisfactory as the data processing activities to send or retrieve the data to/from a FROST/STApplus server are executed in a faster way. Indeed, the speed to successfully sending or retrieving data hosted on a FROST/STApplus server is increased from a factor between 4 and 5 compared to the implementation lacking the multithreading feature provided by the Java programming language.

In the case of Pilot 2, the enhancement of the Terrestrial Connectivity algorithm itself, was also an important factor regarding the scalability. The original computation of the Terrestrial Connectivity Index (ICT) based on Marull J., Mallarach J.M. (2005) was performed pixel by pixel using a big amount of sequential batch processing commands. This ended up with really big batch files difficult to manipulate and execute (i.e., 291 Mb and 1233451 lines for an image with just 85 files and 691 columns, with a pixel of 390 m of spatial resolution). These batch files were command lines executing several MiraMon GIS software¹ independent modules (called MSA for MiraMon Support Apps). An important improvement was the development of a single MiraMon MSA for calculating the Connectivity Index, ICT. This stand-alone tool is able to calculate the index in a more computational efficient way, in which, no batch file is needed and created, and some parts of the images are kept in memory during the different steps of the process, resulting

¹ https://www.miramon.cat/Index_eng.htm

in execution times that are significantly lower. Some processes at 390 m of spatial resolution which took 59.52 of computational hours in the previous batch procedure, it takes approximately 7 hours with the new MSA. A recommendation can be elaborated based on these results: a good balance between granularity and scalability should be done to ensure a low number of necessary computational hours.

However, when some computations are needed at finer resolutions and broader scales, as for instance, the whole Catalan region at 30 m of spatial resolution, this new approach still takes so many machine and time resources that could only be calculated for 2 periods of time: 1987 and 2022. In this case of finer spatial resolutions, ML was needed to give some approximation. The issue has been that whereas ML can be helpful, it also needs to have a substantial number of training images to extract some fine patterns. These training images were very poor for the models as they were only available for 1987 and 2022 as already shown in the deliverable D5.1. More details on this can be found in the deliverables D5.1 and D5.2.

A cache was also implemented and tested to improve the scalability and the performance. The cache was put in place on a Graphical User Interface (GUI) when retrieving a large amount of data stored on a FROST/STApplus server that uses the OGC SensorThings API. The results of this experiment demonstrate that this optimisation allows handling a bigger quantity of data at the same time than initially expected. The use of the cache has accelerated the time needed to retrieve the data hosted by a FROST/STApplus server with a factor of 300.

The utilisation of queuing systems allows an improvement of the performance and the scalability. In the context of the Green Deal Data Space (GDSS), the AD4GD project has designed an architecture taking into account this point. Indeed, the components responsible for the data storage have an interface supporting the MQTT communication protocol. These building blocks are namely the FROST/STApplus server instances and the MinIO database instances. This protocol is using the mechanism of publish/subscribe as message queue service. It means that the delivery of messages through the MQTT communication protocol is more reliable and the Quality of Service (QoS) is better than a synchronous mechanism. As MQTT was designed for IoT devices, the implementation of the MQTT protocol is lightweight and don't require an important energy consumption. Furthermore, the MQTT protocol supports the TLS and SSL protocols for encrypting the connections between the IoT sensors and the data storage components.

Finally, an important point to take care when developing a solution like the Green Deal Data Space is the extensibility which is a part of the scalability. Indeed, the proposed GDSS can be extended with other building blocks and other types of data, in particular considering new use cases related to the environmental data to be added to the GDSS. To achieve this objective, a modular approach was chosen in the design of the future GDSS. The building blocks are available on GitHub at <https://github.com/AD4GD> and they can be downloaded in function of the

needs and use cases of the different stakeholders involved in the exploitation of the Green Deal Data Space. Of course, any new component can be added to the AD4GD GitHub in the future to enrich and extend the possibilities offered by the GDDS.

For instance, the collection of data from different data sources, like Copernicus, Eurostat and the Open Meteo for the city of Berlin, was also undertaken to demonstrate the extensibility and the scalability of the proposed solution concerning the future Green Deal Data Space. The data collection is working and the data can be reused by the other project assets. It is also possible to reuse the data from other components and building blocks of the AD4GD project through the OGC SensorThings API. Indeed, the data are available directly on the different FROST/STApplus server instances installed during the whole duration of the project. Furthermore, it is also envisioned to exchange data with other FROST server instances located outside the Green Deal Data Space, through the OGC SensorThings API, if it is needed for a specific use case.

3 PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

The performance and its assessment permit to evaluate if the proposed concept of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) and its architecture developed in the context of the AD4GD project are coherent in regards of the expectation from the three pilots.

The following sections describe the methodology, the experiments and the outcomes related to the aspects directly linked to the performance encountered in the proposed design and implementation of the GDDS.

3.1 METHODOLOGY AND EXPERIMENTS

The AD4GD project is using an agile approach concerning the development and the implementation of the building blocks and components design for the Green Deal Data Space. Different experiments and tests were undertaken during the whole duration of the project to ensure that the functionalities are working properly and that the performance is aligned with the needs and requirements elaborated by the three pilots.

The methodology used for the performance assessment analyses the most relevant requirements from the pilots and their links to the performance. The next step is to realise some experiments and tests to assess the performance in the relation with the GDDS. An iterative approach is used during the development phase of the building blocks and components of the GDDS and depending on the obtained results, corrective actions are undertaken in the source code of the building blocks for instance. Other measures consist of optimisation of the servers' and clients' settings used in the context of the data collection and processing in the AD4GD project.

An important point to mention is the fact that the performance and the scalability are closely related. Indeed, several experiments done in the context of the scalability assessment and described in the previous sections of this document can obviously improve the global performance of the proposed Green Deal Data Space. For instance, the concurrency implemented in different components to ensure the scalability improves the performance for the data communication.

The following list presents several requirements and needs elaborated by the pilots and associated to the performance:

1. Upload: This aspect is particularly important for the big data to be transmitted, handled and saved into the GDDS components. In the context of the pilots, it is usual to process different kinds of data which are voluminous. Indeed, different data sources are used in the AD4GD project and they provide large datasets to be processed and stored in the components of the GDDS. All the operations done in this context should be performant.
2. Download: This requirement is particularly relevant for a large amount of data stored on a FROST/STApplus server or on a MinIO database. Different building blocks and components need to retrieve the different types of data in an efficient way. For example, a chart plugin, a Graphical User Interface (GUI) or an AI/ML module can read a great amount of data from the storage building blocks. These operations should not be too long, in particular when generating the visualisation of the data, for instance on a map or on a chart, for the users in front of their screen. One other point is the optimisation of the infrastructure to run the calculations close to the data, which is reducing the need to download the data over the Internet. For example, some data processing activities were undertaken at the edge to reduce the amount of data to be uploaded to the FROST/STApplus server: this was applied to data generated by the IoT sensors as explained in the deliverable D3.3 "Scalability and edge computing optimization".
3. Asynchronous upload: This point concerns the tiny data or the files with a limited size to be stored in the related building blocks of the Green Deal Data Space. It is usual that the heterogeneous IoT sensors deployed in the AD4GD pilots are sending their data through tiny packets on the network, as they are measuring in general a limited number of environmental properties. In this case, a system collecting the data in an asynchronous way is pertinent to improve first of all the performance, but also the scalability.
4. Short response times: It is important to have reduced response times from the servers being part of the GDDS architecture designed by the AD4GD project. In particular, client facing components and other building blocks should be user-friendly. Low latency should be in this case guaranteed.
5. Concurrency handling: The concurrency and the parallelism allow a better scalability as demonstrated in the previous dedicated sections, but also improve the global

performance of the future GDDS. Different parallel processes are put in place in the GDDS building blocks thanks to the concurrency.

6. Error handling: The errors are generally reducing the performance of a given computing system. Typical example are the timeouts on the Internet connections. A good handling of errors can reduce the waiting times and improve the performance. As there are different sorts of interconnected building blocks and components on the GDDS architecture, it is very important to avoid bottlenecks and blocking situations when the different kinds of data are transmitted during the execution of the use cases elaborated by the three pilots.

3.2 RESULTS

This section explains the experiments related to the performance executed during the development and the exploitation of the building blocks and components of the future Green Deal Data Space (GDDS). It presents the results of these experiments based on the requirements and needs of the three AD4GD pilots.

First of all, the upload of large amounts of data was scheduled and experimented in the context of the three AD4GD pilots. For instance, the pilot on the air quality is using the data from different types of air quality sensors which are directly connected to the Sensor.Community service. Each month, Sensor.Community releases an archive for every sort of air quality sensors and each archive can represent several GB of air quality data. The project is retrieving the data provided by the Sensor.Community under the form of compressed files containing the archived CSV files. The next step is to convert the data from these files into JSON files compliant to the OGC SensorThings API and to the semantic interoperability put in place and published on the RAINBOW server². After this processing, the data are sent to a FROST/STApplus server for the storage. All the operations done in this data flow should be performant. Different tests were executed to find the most efficient way to send the data to the FROST/STApplus server. First of all, each CSV file was read line by line and the processing consisted to convert the content of a line to a HTTP POST request to the FROST/STApplus server. This request employed the basic features offered by the OGC SensorThings API, but the results in terms of performance were not sufficient, in particular concerning the time needed to store the full content of a given big CSV file. Typically, several days were necessary to process the content of a CSV file of around 10 GB. Then, new approaches were studied and tested. Finally, the good choice is to use the advanced features of the OGC SensorThings API, notably the possibility to realise batch requests. A batch request allows to create new entities like Things, Datastreams and MultiDatastreams and to send the observations at the same time. A huge improvement related to the performance was spotted and the time needed to store all the datasets originally contained in the CSV files was considerably reduced. For instance, one batch request can handle 1000 lines of a CSV file, which

² <https://defs-hosted.opengis.net/prez-hosted/>

reduces the total amount of time to process the whole CSV file. To improve again the performance of the upload, the multi-threaded processing was enabled in the source code of the Java scripts used to process, convert and send the data to the FROST/STApplus server. The choice of the Java programming language is motivated by the better support of the concurrency and the multi-threading by Java compared to other programming languages such as Python.

The download of the different datasets should be performant and several use cases were studied during the AD4GD project. Indeed, several building blocks and components retrieve the datasets stored on the MinIO database or the FROST/STApplus server. For example, the AI/ML module reads the raw data saved on the MinIO server and realised the predictions based on them. It means that the reading should not take too much time. The same constraint applies to the Graphical User Interface (GUI) which displays the data. As there are users in front of their screen, the reading of the data from the databases employed by the GDDS building blocks should be relatively fast to avoid that the users must wait a long time to see the data visualised on their respective screen. To ensure a fast download, different experiments were undertaken to improve the performance of the download.

Final results of the pilots 1, 2, and 3:

- Pilot 1 AI module is focused on providing water level predictions for 17 lakes reporting water level and precipitation measurements for the next 7 days after the date of the last reported sample. This happens every Monday, when all raw data from the previous week is uploaded into the central repository. This triggers the data harmonization process and then the predictions generation. This involves 17 specific models (one model per each lake), each model taking from the central repository the last 200 registries with water level and precipitations data to produce the predictions for the next 7 days considering three different scenarios: i) no precipitations during the incoming days; ii) normal estimated precipitations range; and iii) high expected precipitations. These predictions results are stored in JSON-LD harmonised format in the project's repository and made available for the consumers' services. The processes of harmonising the raw data and producing the corresponding prediction files take between 10 and 15 seconds per lake. In total, less than 3 minutes are necessary to have all the predictions ready to be shown in the corresponding user interfaces. Each prediction file weighs less than 25 kb, so the download time is not significant.
- Pilot 2 works on demand through an API REST that receives an image to be analysed and returning the processed image by the selected biodiversity AI model. The response time here depends on the size and resolution of the input image. The higher is the resolution and the larger is the image size, the longer is the response time. For the images processed within pilot 2, we got response times between 1 minute (for the common analysed use cases) and 25 minutes for big images (whole Catalonia maps).

These response times can be improved by increasing the dedicated resources for AI inferencing, but this is not necessarily linear.

- The machine learning components developed in Pilot 3 were designed with lightweight and efficient implementations in mind, ensuring compatibility with limited-resource environments while allowing for scale-up when needed. The core of the data-driven detection scheme is implemented in Numba, enabling just-in-time (JIT) compilation and significantly accelerating execution speed compared to pure Python approaches. This makes it feasible to process large volumes of sensor data without requiring specialized hardware. A central computational element in the Pilot 3 processing chain is the regridding via ordinary and universal kriging, implemented using PyTorch. This allows the code to run effectively on both CPUs and GPUs. The regridding has already proven to scale well, as demonstrated by the successful generation of various Pilot 3 datasets. While CPU execution may be sufficient for batch-mode analyses in offline or reprocessing workflows, real-time or near-real-time applications clearly benefit from GPU use, where speedups of 60–100x over CPU have been observed for the different Pilot 3 datasets. The overall design of the Pilot 3 components is flexible and modular, which makes it easy to adapt them for different use cases. Since they do not rely on specific hardware or platforms, they can be used both in research and in more operational environments.

The use of a dedicated middleware placed between a FROST/STApplus server and a Graphical User Interface permits to reduce the workload of this GUI. The middleware handles all the requests to be sent to the FROST/STApplus server to obtain the data and manages all the connections between the FROST/STApplus server and itself. So, the GUI is not taking care at all of the communication with the FROST/STApplus server and doesn't need to implement the OGC SensorThings API. The results are very good concerning the performance: the time to download the data from a FROST/STApplus server is reduced with a factor comprised between 4 and 5.

The utilisation of a cache on the Graphical User Interface is also improving the performance and also, the user-friendliness. The cache avoids to request each time the data stored on the FROST/STApplus server. This is particularly useful when the data are not changing a lot of, such as the historical data which can be considered at the end as static data. In conclusion for the part related to download, a dedicated middleware associated to a cache is the good solution to reduce the time of downloads form the datasets stored on a FROST/STApplus server instance.

The asynchronous upload is also a good mechanism improving the performance and the scalability of the proposed GDDS design. Indeed, the asynchronous upload is implemented in the GDDS architecture through a queueing system based on the MQTT communication protocol. Both FROST/STApplus server and MinIO database offer MQTT interfaces used to send the data to be saved in the Green Deal Data Space. The MQTT communication protocol permits to be immediately notified when new datasets are received by both GDDS components. After a

notification, the received data are placed in the queue and then, handled properly by the GDDS building blocks. In terms of performance, the MQTT protocol brings a reduction of the Internet traffic as it is less verbose and complex for the management of the connections than the HTTP communication protocol. Furthermore, the MQTT protocol is dedicated to real-time communication, which is of course the case for IoT devices. As different sorts of IoT sensors are deployed in the different locations of the pilots, it is also important for the performance to have an architecture for the Green Deal Data Space supporting asynchronous upload and a large number of IoT sensors generating the environmental data.

The following requirement associated to the performance inside the Green Deal Data Space (GDSS) is the faster response times. This point is very important when the services linked to the GDDS are directly available to the users. For instance, all the Graphical User Interface (GUI) components should be user-friendly and one of the key aspects of the user-friendliness is to limit as much as possible the waiting times for the users. This is in fact quite challenging as a large number of datasets can be retrieved to the AD4GD storage components, such the FROST/STApplus server or the MinIO database. The data processing activities realised by the AI/ML module are also time consuming due the large quantity and volume of data used to train the models for the different sorts of predictions. The agile developments on the different GDDS building blocks permit to improve the performance through iterative versions of every building blocks.

Furthermore, several mechanisms were implemented to reduce the response times in the different GDDS components. Some of these mechanisms were already presented in this deliverable in the chapter dedicated to the scalability. For example, the upload of the data was improved to reduce the time and in the other direction, the utilisation of caching mechanisms allows the reduction of the download time. As already mentioned, the MQTT communication protocol is a good choice to avoid slow response times, thanks to the integrated queueing system. This is also directly linked to the following requirement on the concurrency: the combination of a queueing system and the concurrency implemented through the multi-threading brings better performance in terms of response times inside the GDDS architecture developed in the context of the AD4GD project. Some related experiments were already described in the deliverable D3.2 "Scalability and edge computing optimization".

Finally, an important work was done by all the partners to handle all the errors encountered, particularly in the raw data. Indeed, some data collected from external sources, like the Berlin Wasserportal, were incomplete or contained erroneous data. Pre-processing activities were put in place to handle the errors contained in the data. For instance, incomplete or wrong data were removed or ignored by the GDDS building blocks where it is necessary. Errors coming from the transmissions, particularly for the IoT sensors deployed in the remote areas where the network connections are not always good, are still possible, but several GDDS building blocks incorporate different filters to remove these errors or to simply ignore the wrong data. Some detailed

explanations are given in the deliverables directly linked to the concerned GDDS building blocks and components.

3.3 FUTURE WORK

In this document we have not analyzed the impact of the use of the Eclipse Dataspace Connector in the architecture. Indeed, other members of the GDDS should use the EDC to access the data in the GDDS providers following the dataspace protocol. The negotiation of contracts and the use of virtual URL to get access to the data have implications in the performance of the GDDS final solution. We were not able to conduct such study due to the constantly evolving versions of the EDC that has included the capacities that we ended only in last version released a few month before the end of the project. Details on the EDC implementation in AD4GD can be found in Deliverable D4.3 "Connecting the Green Deal Data Space".

4 TECHNOLOGY CONVERGENCE ASSESSMENT

The technology convergence is an important point to take into account in the context of the deployment and the exploitation of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS). The utilisation of common technologies across the GDDS building blocks permits to have a solid architecture of the Green Deal Data Space which can be extended relatively easily. Furthermore, common technologies facilitate the interoperability of the different GDDS components and the reuse of the GDDS building blocks is also simplified.

This section presents the different experiments and actions undertaken during the whole duration of the AD4GD project concerning the technology convergence. Of course, some evolutions can be expected in the near future when more components for the GDDS will be available or updated.

4.1 METHODOLOGY AND EXPERIMENTS

The technology convergence depends on the architecture of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS). Each component or building block of the GDDS designed in the context of the AD4GD project has at least one interface to communicate with the other building blocks using standard protocols and formats. Different technologies are used by the interfaces in function of the communication layer. During the first phases of the AD4GD project, the partners employed an iterative approach to design the GDDS architecture and the related components and building blocks. Finally, several important technologies were chosen and put in place to ensure a reliable and efficient communication among the GDDS building blocks: the OGC SensorThings API, the related data model, and the semantic interoperability. The following section presents the results of this

process of adding technologies to the GDDS architecture and then, to ensure the technology convergence and the related interoperability.

4.2 RESULTS

The OGC SensorThings API represents the core of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) designed by the AD4GD partners. Indeed, almost all types of data collected during the AD4GD project, in particular the data used and generated by the three pilots, can be stored on a FROST/STApplus server. To achieve this, the raw data are converted to the data model enforced by the OGC SensorThings API specification. The usage of the OGC SensorThings API permits to ease the exchange of data, in particular the data generated by the heterogeneous IoT sensors deployed in the three pilots. It means that the GDDS building blocks compliant to the OGC SensorThings API standard can easily transmit or retrieve data to or from other components or building blocks using also the OGC SensorThings API. This brings a good interoperability inside the Green Deal Data Space, but also outside the GDDS if the data should be shared to other external stakeholders.

From the OGC SensorThings API, a related data model was selected and extended to fulfil the objectives of the AD4GD project, in particular the implementation of the FAIR principles. Of course, this data model is based on the OGC SensorThings API specification. This data model was extended to implement the FAIR principles. Concretely, new entities were introduced in the basic data model provided by the OGC SensorThings API specification. The notion of Party, License, Campaign, ObservationGroup and Relation were added to the data model under the form of entities. This addition allows a better management of the data, mainly on the aspects linked to the licenses. The extended data model is the basis for the implementation of the GDDS building blocks and ensures a good understanding of the properties commonly used in the future GDDS.

The semantic interoperability is also playing an important role in the GDDS as it ensures that each variable used in different components and building blocks available in the GDDS is understood in a clear manner and that its interpretation is correct for all the stakeholders involved in the Green Deal Data Space. An important work has been done to semantically describe the Essential Variables, i.e., the Essential Biodiversity Variables, by using the I-ADOPT framework ontology³, expose them in TTL or JSON-LD formats, and publish them into the OGC RAINBOW server available at <https://defs-hosted.opengis.net/prez-hosted/>. The semantic interoperability is a good technology to avoid misinterpretation of the metadata and data collected from various sources distributed in Europe mainly. The convergence of the Earth Observation (EO) is considered through the I-ADOPT framework.

³ <https://i-adopt.github.io/ontology/>

5 GLOBAL RESULTS

The iterative developments of the different AD4GD building blocks designed for the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) were conducted with several experiments and tests. This approach permits to continuously improve the performance and the scalability based on the test results, and to ensure the interoperability thanks to the technology convergence.

For each pilot, the results obtained at the end of the AD4GD project are good concerning the aspects described in this deliverable. Indeed, the results of the experiments demonstrate that the scalability, the performance and the technology convergence are aligned with the requirements and needs announced by the three pilots during the initial phases of the project. In particular, the challenges associated to the heterogeneity of the data encountered by the three AD4GD pilots are well addressed and the different components and building blocks are able to process the pilot data in a proper way, with the expected performance and scalability.

Finally, it means that the basis of the future GDDS designed and proposed by the AD4GD project is solid and can evolve in the good direction in a future project on the topics related to the environmental data.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the tests executed in relation with the scalability, the performance and the technology convergence in the three AD4GD pilots have demonstrated the pertinence of the Green Deal Data Space design proposed by all the partners during the whole duration of the project. From these results, some recommendations can be elaborated:

- The replicability and the scalability can be ensured by starting from the existing infrastructure. Indeed, the implementation of a HPC cluster through Kubernetes allows the replication of the cluster in another data centre or infrastructure, and on the other hand, the extension and the scale-up of its current implementation is facilitated by the containerisation of the components which can be quickly deployed on Kubernetes. The utilisation of Docker containers in the development phase has accelerated the preparation and the execution of several tests realised in the context of the deliverable D6.3. These elements should take into account in the future developments of components and building blocks dedicated to the Green Deal Data Space.
- The processing of data at the edge is important, in particular for IoT sensors sending their data to the building blocks of the GDDS. Indeed, the scalability and the performance of the global GDDS can be improved significantly if the data processing at the edge is properly implemented. It allows the reduction of the network bandwidth, in particular for constrained devices, such as the IoT sensors installed in the different pilots. This

point should be also considered for future deployments of the GDDS in a real environment.

- The storage capacity is also a topic to take into consideration. In the different pilots, conversions of large amounts of raw data were undertaken to obtain datasets which can reuse by the components and the building blocks of the Green Deal Data Space. To avoid repeatedly conversions of the same data, in particular the historical data, it is important to have a sufficient storage capacity for FAIR data in the GDDS architecture. Furthermore, it allows a quick access to existing datasets which are fully compliant to the FAIR principles and to semantic interoperability put in place during the AD4GD project. A replication of some raw data into the GDDS can be also done in the case of technical issues, such as network issues, appearing to the third-party data producers.
- The computing resources should be sufficiently allocated to the AI/ML modules to obtain fast and good results to the users. The utilisation of Just-In-Time (JIT) compilation, such as Numba in this project, provides some improvements related to the performance and the scalability. Of course, as the research on the Artificial Intelligence is one of the main topics in the different universities and research centres, some important progresses can be expected in the coming years and better performance could be reached in the near future.
- To facilitate the integration of future data sources associated to the environment in the GDDS, it is expected to use APIs from other external data providers. In this case, it would be important for the developers to have a good documentation and some useful examples on how to use all the features offered by such APIs. It would ensure that this kind of integration is aligned with the requirements of performance and scalability expected in the Green Deal Data Space.
- Related to the previous point, the ideal case of integration is that each external data provider is able to provide its data using the OGC SensorThings API specification. At the same time, the semantic interoperability should be ensured by using the outcomes of the AD4GD project not only for the data, but also for the metadata. It means that an external data provider should ideally follow the guidance on the semantic interoperability put in place in the project.

In this document we have not analyzed the impact of the use of the Eclipse Dataspace Connector in the architecture. Indeed, other members of the GDDS should use the EDC to access the data in the GDDS providers following the dataspace protocol. The negotiation of contracts and the use of virtual URL to get access to the data have implications in the performance and scalability of the solution. We were not able to conduct such study due to the constantly evolving versions of the EDC that has included the capacities that we ended only in last version released a few month before the end of the project. Details on the EDC implementation in AD4GD can be found in Deliverable D4.3 "Connecting the Green Deal Data Space".

7 REFERENCES

AD4GD Project 101061001. GRANT AGREEMENT. European Research Executive Agency (REA)

AD4GD Project 101061001. Deliverable D5.1 AI, ML in HPC and cloud for FAIR Science Services

AD4GD Project 101061001. Deliverable D3.2 Scalability and edge computing optimization

AD4GD Project 101061001. Deliverable D5.2 Artificial intelligence resources for Earth system modeling

Marull J., Mallarach J.M. (2005). A GIS methodology for assessing ecological connectivity: application to the Barcelona Metropolitan Area. *Landscape and Urban Planning*. Volume 71, Issues 2–4. Pages 243-262.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2004.03.007>

AD4GD Project 101061001. Deliverable D4.3 Connecting the Green Deal Data Space